
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND JOB INVOLVEMENT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Authors

⁽¹⁾Dr. Barnabas E. Nwankwo-Department of Psychology Caritas University Enugu, Nigeria

⁽²⁾Solomon A. Agu-Department of Psychology Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria

⁽³⁾Dr. Ngozi Sydney-Abor-Department of Psychology, Imo State University Owerri, Nigeria

⁽⁴⁾Chimezie E. Chikwendu-Department of Psychology, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement among secondary school teachers in Ihube, Okigwe Imo State. A total of 80 participants comprising forty six (46) male and thirty four (34) female teachers were drawn using simple random sampling. They were between the ages of 26-59 years, with a mean age of 38.6 years. The choice of design was correlational design. Two Questionnaires were used in the study which was a 20-item Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire and a 6-item Job Involvement Subscale. Statistical analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient revealed a significant relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement among employees $r(78)=0.56, P<.05$. The results and implications were discussed and suggestions made for further researches.

Keywords: school teachers, job satisfaction, job involvement, job characteristics, nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Job satisfaction is how content an individual is with his or her job. On job satisfaction, Locke and Luthans (1990) gave a comprehensive definition of job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from appraisal of one's job or experience. Job satisfaction is a personal feeling of contentment which a worker has and exhibits towards his or her work situation. Cormick and Igan (1990) also defined job satisfaction as a reflection of the match between what workers want from job and what they actually receive. On the other hand, Mitchell and Lasan (1987) note that job satisfaction is generally recognized in the organizational behavior field as the most important and frequently studied attitude. Hulin (1991) stated that job with responsibility may be dissatisfying to some because of stress and problem that co-vary with responsibility. Others may find responsibility a source of positive effects, challenging jobs may be satisfying to some because of how they feel about themselves after completing difficult job assignments; others may find such self-administered

rewards irrelevant. In other words, most people prefer work that is challenging and stimulating over work that is predicted and routine (Robbins & Judge, 2009). According to Alexander, Linchtenstein and Hellman(1997). Lack of job satisfaction is a predictor of quitting a job. Sometimes workers quit from the public to the private sector and vice versa. This movement is common in countries grappling with dwindling economy and its commitment such as poor condition of service and late payment of salaries. Blau and Boal (1987) asserted that employees who are highly satisfied with their jobs or strongly committed to the organization and will avoid withdrawal behavior and maintain continued attachment to work. It has been suggested that when employees are highly satisfied they will come out about the quality of their work and become committed to the organization. This includes having high retention rates and being more productive. They are also of the opinion that dissatisfied employees are more likely to say they will be leaving the organization soon. Also, such employees are not likely to recommend their work places to a friend, potentially making it more problematic for an

organization to recruit fulltime employees. In Nigeria public service employees have clearly demonstrated their love for salary increase for the continuing stay on the job rather than improved conditions of service. More so, when employees receive high wages and salaries; there is a tendency that they will have high job satisfaction (Aremu, 1998). Job involvement is the level of psychological identification with one job (Kanugo, 1982). A person with high level of job involvement tends to be satisfied with their job and highly committed to their career, professions, and employing organizations (Brown, Carson, and Bedelan, 1995; Cohen, 1995). Moreover, these individuals hardly ever think about changing employers and generally believe that their personal goal and the organizational goals are aligned (Brown, 1995). Conversely, low job involved employees have been found empirically to be more likely to leave the organization or withdrawal effort towards the job and either apply that energy to tasks outside the realm of work or engage in various undesirable activities on the job (Kanugo, 1979). However, job involvement have also been described as one of the characteristics of an individual something which is “inside” the person that he or she brings to a job and is of course related to other personal characteristics. Job involvement has also been found to be related to situational job characteristics (Lawler & Hall, 1970). Operationalization of job involvement includes job identification, participation and the connection of job value with self-worth (Blau, 1986). Paullay, Alliger and Stone-Romero, (1994) defined job involvement as the degree to which one is cognitively preoccupied with one’s present job. This definition distinguished two components of job involvement which are job involvement in the role and job involvement in the settings. Job involvement is deduced to be as the maximum when an individual is for an employee to be highly involved in one component and lowly involved in the other. For example an employee can be very involved in a specific job but not be committed to the organization or vice-versa (Blau & Boal, 1987). Robinson and Shaver (1973) defined job involvement as the degree to which the employees of an organization are willing to work accordingly. Individuals willing to work hard are said to be highly job involved,

whereas individuals without the willingness are considered lowly job involved. Lodahi and Kejnar (1965) defined job involvement as the degree to which a person is identified psychologically with his work or the importance of work in his total self-image. They added that where there is high degree of identification with work, the internalization of value judgments about the goodness or importance of work serves as a psychological surrogate for the goodness of the individual performing the work. This study will determine if there is a relationship between job satisfaction, and job involvement among school teachers.

Theoretical Background

Maslow’s (1954) need hierarchy theory revealed that a motivated worker stands the chance of being satisfied with his or her job in an organization. Locke (1976) value discrepancy theory explains that satisfaction is determined by a discrepancy between what one wants in a job and what one has in a job. Herzberg’s motivator – hygiene theory (1959) explained that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by different factors. Satisfaction depends on motivators like (recognition, promotion, opportunities etc) while dissatisfaction is as the result of hygiene factors like (pay, company policies etc.). Landy (1978, 1985) opponent process theory viewed job satisfaction as an emotional state that is subject to physiological influences. A highly satisfying job can become routine and boring through such processes. Dispositional theory states that people have innate dispositions that cause them to have tendencies towards a certain level of satisfaction regardless of one’s job. Each of the theory summarized the field extensively and observed the limited influence of satisfaction on work input and output. They all specify the particular needs that must be satisfied or the values that must be attained for an individual to be satisfied with his job. Recent researches suggested that people must find their work satisfying on order to be motivated to do a satisfactory job. Abiodun (2012), investigated the current job satisfaction level of primary school teachers. Two hundred and thirty eight teachers (males 95 and females 143) randomly selected from twenty primary schools from public and private schools in Ota, Ogun State participated

in the survey. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentage one way analysis of variance and t-test statistic. The results of the two research question and two research hypotheses indicated that greater percentage of teachers (52.9%) were very satisfied with their job while it is also evident that female teachers were very happy with their job that male teachers. Further analysis showed that no significant difference existed on gender basis while there were significant difference on educational qualification and age groups. Consequent upon these findings, it is imperative for proprietors of schools to ensure that teachers are not dissatisfied with their job through their inability to consistently provide enabling environment.

Hypothesis

There will be a significant relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement among school teachers.

METHODS

Design/Statistics

The design for the study was correlational design. It was chosen because the researchers seek to ascertain if a relationship exists between two linearly related variables (job satisfaction and job involvement) without the manipulation of any of the variables. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient was used for data analysis to determine if a relationship exists between job satisfaction and job involvement.

Participants

The participants comprised 80 (46 male and 36 female) teachers drawn from 2 different secondary schools in Ihube, Okigwe Local Government of Imo State namely; Ihube Boys High School and Girls Secondary School Ihube after approvals were given. The norms reported below are the mean scores obtained by workers in the general population.

by the authorities of the secondary schools. The participants were selected using random sampling technique. The mean age of participants was 38.6 years. While their ages ranged from 20-59 years. With regards to marital status 51 participants were married and 29 participants were single. According to educational qualification 2 had professional diploma, 28 NCE, 1 HND, 38 B.Sc., and 11. M.Sc. No participant had a Ph.D.

Measures

Job Satisfaction Scale

Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire developed by Weiss, Dawis, England, Lofquist (1967) was used. It is a 20-item questionnaire designed to examine certain prevailing situation in workplace. Three component of job fulfilment will be obtained with this inventory. They are intrinsic satisfaction (I), extrinsic satisfaction (E), and, General satisfaction (G). The items are worded 1-Very dissatisfied, 2-Dissatisfied, 3-Not sure, 4-Satisfied and 5-Very satisfied. A least possible score of 20 and a highest possible score of 100 could be obtained with this questionnaire. The questionnaire was used for this study because it assesses job satisfaction which is the fulfilment the job environment provides a worker. Example of questions in this questionnaire include: (Being able to keep busy all the time, the chance to work alone on the job).The questionnaire was scored by adding together the values of the numbers shaded in the relevant items that constitute each of the three components. For example if in items 2,3,4,5,6,7 the numbers shaded are 1,5,4,2,3,1 respectively. The score for the six items is $1+5+4+2+3+1=16$. Weiss et al. (1967) provided the psychometric properties for the American samples while Mogaji (1997) provided the psychometric properties for the Nigerian samples for the Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire (MSQ).

	American samples	Nigerian
	M&F (n=1, p723)	M&F (n=600)
Intrinsic	47.14	40.22
Extrinsic	19.98	18.32
General	74.85	65.13

Weiss et al (1967) reported a one week interval test-retest reliability coefficient of 0.89. A one year interval coefficient of 0.70 for the Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire.

Job Involvement Scale

Job involvement was measured using adopted questions from the Organisational Commitment scale developed by Buchanan (1974). It is a 6-item questionnaire that measures job involvement of workers. Example of questions in this scale include: (The major satisfaction in my life comes from my job). The scale uses both direct and reverse scoring of items:-

Direct scoring: - Add together the values of the numbers shaded in the relevant items. For example if in items 4,5,6. The numbers shaded are 7,5,4 respectively. The score for the three items is 7+5+4=16. The directly scored items in the scale are numbers 1,2,3,4,5.

Reverse scoring:- Change the values of the numbers from 1,2,3,4,5,6,7 to 7,6,5,4,3,2,1 Respectively and add together the reverse values of the numbers shaded in the relevant items. If in item 1,2,3,4 the numbers shaded are 7,3,4,5 respectively the score for the four items is 1+5+4+3=13. The reversely scored items in the scale are numbers 2 and 6. The psychometric properties for the job involvement scale were provided by the following: Buchanan (1974) provided part of the psychometric property for the British samples. While the other parts of the properties were provided through extrapolation by sources from which some of the scales where derived. The psychometric properties for the Nigerian samples were also extrapolated from those provided by Mogaji (1997). The norms reported below are mean score obtained by workers in the general population.

Scale	British samples	Nigerian
Samples	M (n=390)	M&F(n=600)
Job Involvement	33.98	28.54

Buchanan (1974) reported co-efficient alpha of 0.84 for the job involvement scale. The Nigerian Norms or mean scores are the basis for interpreting the scores of participants. Scores higher than the norms indicate adequate job satisfaction/job involvement in the particular component of the scale while scores lower than the norms indicate dissatisfaction/low job involvement.

Procedures

The instruments were administered to the respondents in their various institutions during the break periods. Copies of the instrument were distributed to the respondents accompanied by a covering letter encouraging participants and ensuring confidentiality. The questionnaires were completed and returned on the spot by the participants. Data collection took about one week and all participants correctly completed the questionnaire.

RESULTS

Summary table of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on The Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Job Involvement

Variables	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY	N	Df	r	P
Job Satisfaction	6833		586994		191853	80	78	0.56	<.05
Job Involvement		2214		68551					

The summary table above shows that r-calculated value of r=0.56 was found to be greater than P-critical value of P<.05. Therefore the hypothesis which stated that "There will be a significant relationship between job

satisfaction and job involvement" is hereby accepted. A statistical significant positive relationship exist between job satisfaction and job involvement level of secondary school teachers in Ngwo, Enugu $R = (78).0.56$, $P < .05$. This shows that an increase in job satisfaction leads to an increase in job involvement and vice versa

DISCUSSION

The outcome of this study indicates that there is a significant relationship between the level of job satisfaction and the level of job involvement of employees. Hence the hypothesis tested which stated that "There will be no significant relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement" was disconfirmed. This is because an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees will also lead to an increase in also the level of job involvement and also the possibility of staying or continuing in the same organisation by the employee. In other words, employees' have a significantly related degree of job satisfaction and job involvement as Secondary School Teachers in Ihube Okigwe, Imo State. Previous researches have shown that in order to increase job involvement, volunteers must fulfil their needs to achieve and obtain job satisfaction. This is because an increase in certain facets of job satisfaction (pay, promotion, and promotion opportunities) can lead to increase in the level of job involvement of employees. The findings of Parker (2006), suggest that a significant relationship exist between job satisfaction, job involvement and organisational commitment. According to the observations of Knoop (1986), job involvement was not related to overall satisfaction, but to only two specific facets (satisfaction with work and promotion opportunity). In contrast, the degree of relationship between overall and various facets of job satisfaction and commitment and between involvement and commitment was moderately high. They are also of the opinion that dissatisfied employees are more likely to say they will be leaving the organisation soon. But evidently, job satisfaction and job involvement were found to be positively related. This implies that as job satisfaction increases, job involvement will increase.

Implications of the Findings

The result of this study would help to understand the following:

The nature of job satisfaction and job involvement with regards to employees and would also serve as an important contribution to job satisfaction and job

involvement in Organisations. It will enable the employers of labour to know that employees who experience higher level of job involvement were found to be highly satisfied and are fulfilled in their jobs (Mayer & Allen, 1997).

Recommendations

In view of the above findings the following recommendations were made:

Additional research is needed to elaborate on the findings reported in this study.

Further researches should be conducted on job satisfaction and job involvement to know if it affects other organisational variables such as absenteeism, job performance and organisation productivity. The research setting is limited to only 4 secondary schools in Ngwo, Enugu. There are other schools in the state. The job satisfaction and job involvement level of male and female (gender) and married and single employees (marital status) were not determined. The study is correlational and as such we cannot assume any causal relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers hereby conclude that there is a significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement among school teachers. This implies that as they become highly satisfied with their teaching jobs, they will be more involved in their careers. This will aid policy makers in the educational sector to pay more attention to the overall wellbeing and satisfaction of teachers as this will increase job involvement, efficiency and productivity.

REFERENCES

Abiodun, A. (2012). Job Satisfaction Status of Primary School Teachers in
OTA, Nigeria. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 4(1), 11-18.

Alexander, J.A., Liechtenstein, R.O., & Hellmann, E. (1998). A causal model of

- voluntary turn-over among nursing personnel in long term psychiatric setting. *Research in Nursing and Health*, 21 (5), 415-427.
- Aremu, A.O. (1998): Enhancing Job satisfaction of the Nigerian Police. *Nigerian Journal of Applied Psychology* Vol. 4. No. 1, 44 – 48.
- Blau, G. J. (1986). Job involvement and organizational commitment as interactive predictors of tardiness and absenteeism. *Journal of Management*, 12, 577–584.
- Blau.G.J, &Boal, K.B. (1987). Conceptualizing How Job Involvement and Organizational Commitment Affect Turnover and Absenteeism. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 12, 288-300
- Brown, S.P. (1995). A Meta-Analysis and Review of Organizational Research on Job Involvement. *Psychological Bulletin* 2, 235 – 255.
- Brown, S.P. & Leigh, T.W. (1995). A new look at Psychological Climate and its Relationship to Job Involvement, Effort and Performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 81.358 – 368.
- Cohen, A. 1995. An examination of the relationships between work commitment and nonwork domains. *Human Relations*, 48, 239-263.
- Hellman, C.M. (1997). Job satisfaction and Intent to Leave, *Journal of Social Psychology* 137 (s) 677-689.
- Herzberg, F. (1974). Motivation-hygiene profiles. *Organizational Dynamics*, 3 (2), 18-29.
- Hulin, C.L. (1968). Effect of Changes in Job Satisfaction Level on Employee Turnover, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 52.122-126.
- Kanugo, R.N. (1982). Measurement of Job and Work involvement. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 67 341 – 349.
- Knoop, R. (1986). Job Involvement: An Elusive Concept. *Psychological Report*, 59, 451 – 456.
- Landy, F.J. (1978). An opponent process theory of job satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 63, 533-547.
- Lawler, E.E. & Hall, D.T.(1970). Relationship of Job Characteristics to Job Involvement, Job satisfaction and Intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 54 (4) 305 – 312.
- Locke, L.A. & Luthan, G.P. (1990). Theory of Goal setting and task performance. Eaglewood cliffs. NJ. Prentice Hall.
- Lodati, T.M, & Kejner, M. (1965).The Definition and Measurement of Job Involvement. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 49 (1) 24 – 33.
- Maslow, A.H. (1943). A Theory of Human Motivation, *Psychological Review*, 50, 370 – 376.
- McCormick, E.J. & Ilgen, D.R. (1985). *Industrial and Organisational Psychology*. (8th ed.). London: Allen & Unwin
- Meyer, J. & Allen, N. (1997). *Commitment in the Workplace: Theory, Research and Application*. London: Sage.
- Mogaji, A.A. (1997). *Effect of organisational climate on employees commitment, involvement and motivation in some Nigerian manufacturing*

industries. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Dept. of Psychology, University of Lagos.

Involvement and Work Centrality. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 79 (2) 224-228.

Parker, S. K. (2006). Job satisfaction. In S. G. Rogelberg (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of industrial and organizational psychology* pp. 474–475. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Robinson, J. & Shaver, P. R. (1973). Measures of social psychological attitudes. Ann Arbor, MI: Institute for Social Research.

Paullay, I.M, Alliger, G.M, & Stone – Romero, E.F. (1994). Construct Validation of Two Instruments Designed to Measure Job niversity of Minnesota.

Weiss, D.J. (1967). Manual for the Minesota Satisfaction Questionnaire Minesota Studies in Vocational Rehabilitation. Xx11. U